
Use of Social Media Networking in Libraries

Dr. Rahul R. Dhuldhule

Librarian,

Milind Mahavidyalaya, Mulava, Tq. Umarkhed, Dist-Yavatmal (M.S.)

Corresponding Author - Dr. Rahul R. Dhuldhule

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15559845

Abstract:

This paper examines how Libraries can leverage on social networking and Social Media skills to provide dynamic library services in the face of dwindling economic problems in India. The unprecedented technological advancement of the 21st century, no doubt has impacted on library services globally and in India in particular. The Social Media hype has gradually crept into the library profession with social sites such as Facebook, MySpace, Flickr, YouTube, Library Thing, it has become evident that our services will need to change to meet the growing needs of our end users. Libraries in India have been challenged like never before to render more proactive and more value added services to meet the ever changing needs of our patrons. This paper is therefore, an attempt to examine the present scenario in library services delivery with these new and emerging technologies. Challenges faced by Indian libraries in the use of these Social Media are investigated and possible solutions proffered.

Keywords: *Social Networking, Libraries, Library Services, Face Book, Twitter, Library, Social Networking, Reference Service, Youtube, Flickr, Blog.*

Introduction:

The recent growth and development of social media and the technology that goes along with it has made life simpler for librarians and other library professionals. Social media is the most efficient communication in today's society, where everyone can contact one another with a click. To use in their libraries, library professionals are also becoming familiar with social media and the tools that go along with it. Social media is being implemented by library staff to build a virtual platform for user interaction, and it is also being used to reach out to specific audiences and clients. Librarians use social media to connect with library customers and to sell their sources and services. Several reasons influence the

adoption of social media in libraries because library professionals believe that social media is the greatest way to bring library users closer together. Aside from these facts, library professionals face many obstacles and issues when using social media in their various libraries. These obstacles and concerns must be overcome to use social media more effectively and consistently in libraries. Library personnel use social media to communicate with potential consumers. Academic libraries are increasingly adopting social media platforms to connect users, facilitate services, promote resources, reach out to new audiences, and increase exposure.

Application of Social Media in Libraries:**Social Networking:**

MySpace: Here library users can use html to customize their profile and they can add new graphics and videos on it.

Facebook: With the help of Face book, library users can be informed with different upcoming events and share the information about their new arrivals and editions of books. Face book mainly helps in marketing of services and products. Photo can be tagged through the use of it.

Ask-A: Librarian service can be exploited by using it.

Twitter: Twitter is a free social networking used to send and read messages known as tweets. At present librarians share all kinds of news regarding library through the use of twitter. Librarians can highlight new materials, new groups, meetings and more with some of these suggestions through twitter.

LinkedIn: It is a professional networking site. It can be used by the librarians to create professional connections and to market library services among other library professionals spread all over the world and can also share their ideas and professional experiences.

WEB 2.0: The term was coined by Darcy DiNuccie in 1999 and the term was popularized by Tim O'Reilly⁴. The term includes weblogs, wikis and syndications. It is nearly synonymous with social media.

Blog: Libraries can use Blogs to keep their users aware with the latest developments in the field of library related matter. Blogs can be subscribed through RSS feeds. Blogger and Word Press are the examples of blog. In addition to this blog can be used as follows—

- Notice Board
- Latest arrival
- Current Awareness Service
- User Orientation Programme can be uploaded

Wikis: The most recognized wiki is Wikipedia. A few other wiki services are wikia, wiki how, wiki dot, Wikimedia, wiki news, PB works. Wikis can be used for---

- Collaborative work
- Publication of historical photos and information
- Building relation between librarian and user

Ajax: Ajax, part of web 2.0, is one tool of choice for creating interactive pages with easily changeable components. In libraries web pages can update frequently with new messages with help of Ajax without reloading the entire browser page.

Mashups: It is hybrid of different social media. The users are allowed to edit OPAC data and metadata and create a user driven catalogue.

IM (Instant Messaging): Users can chat with the librarian through IM, an online communication service which is used for reference service and voice chat. Here co-browsing, file sharing, screen capturing and data sharing; etc. are also possible. It is generally communicated through SMS via mobile phone.

YOUTUBE: Libraries can also advocate their different programs, conferences, workshops, seminars, Virtual conferences by uploading their videos on the YouTube.

FLICKR: It is an online image sharing service. Sharing and uploading picture of library events and services are possible for libraries by using Flickr.

RSS: RSS, a collection of web feed formats for publishing frequently updated works, became popular as web users need not to browse frequently the new entry in their preferred website. Feed reader or feed aggregator is needed to read RSS feed. The popular feed readers are blog lines, Google reader, feed demon, etc. In the domain of LIS, RSS may be used for—

- Marketing the library services among distance learner.
- Dissemination of updated news to the web user
- Selective Dissemination of Information
- Sending News to the users according to their area of interest
- Library news, events, orientation, etc.

Social Bookmarking and Tagging:

Social bookmarking is a method for the users of internet to store, organize, search the bookmarks of the web pages on the net with the help of user-driven metadata popularly known as tagging.

Libraries can use social bookmarking web sites to tag and develop online catalog of library resources. Delicious is an online social bookmarking service which store and share the large number of web bookmarks. Other notable bookmarking services are CiteUlike, Diigo, Google Reader, folkd, etc

Librarian 2.0:

In September 2005, Michale Carey used the term “Library 2.0” in his personal blog Library Crunch .When “Web 2.0” is combined with library services, it is renamed as “Lib 2.0” where web users can create the

content and services they view within the library's web-presence, OPAC, etc.

Advantage of use of Social Media:

- Social media is integral to market library
- Social media capture potential users of the library
- Social media offers more than just traditional ways of marketing library services
- Social media helps students to use library
- Social media allows user to create, connect, converse, to contribute, vote and share information
- It helps libraries to get closer to the users
- It helps libraries in building collaborative network with the users

Disadvantage or Problems use of Social Media:

- Too many social media tools to learn
- Lack of time to use social media
- Lack of privacy and identity theft
- Confidentiality of information
- Lack of knowledge how to use it
- Inadequate funding for libraries
- Inadequate library staff
- Low interest of librarians in learning and utilizing social media
- Inadequate training opportunities for library staff
- Electricity failure
- Slow speed of Internet

Reference:

1. Farkas, M. (2007), —Building academic library 2.0, paper

- presented at the Academic Library 2.0 Conference, Norwich University, 2 November
2. Musser, J. and O'Reilly, T. (2007), Web 2.0 Principles and Practices, O'Reilly Media Inc., available at: <http://oreilly.com/radar/web2report.csp> (accessed on 8th February 2016).
 3. Palmateer, J. (2007), —Have risqué info or photos online? It could cost youll, The Daily Star, available at: www.thedailystar.com/local/local_story_349040009.html (accessed 12 February 2016).
 4. Taylor and Francis group. (2014). Use of social media by library: current practices and future opportunities. October 2014.
 5. Use of social media by the library http://blogs.ubc.ca/dean/2010/08/top_100_ways_librarians_use_social_media/ (accessed on 14th February 2016)